

paper Chain

Guidelines for the implementation of
the Circular Economy models.

FACTSHEET CC1a

Lime ash Concrete Pre-casts

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New Market Niches For the Pulp and Paper Industry Waste based on Circular Economy Approaches

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Keywords

Guidelines	Construction material	Pulp & Paper Industry (PPI)	Circular Economy Model (CEM)	Fact sheet
assessment	requirement	standard	Waste	performance
concrete	Lime mud	Lime ash	Pre-cast	porticos

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CC1a – Lime ash Concrete Pre-casts.

CC1a: Lime ash Concrete Pre-casts: lime ash can be employed successfully in the fabrication of pre-cast concrete replacing 100% of natural fillers. Technical and environmental performance achieved user requirements. CC1a CEM has a high replicability potential. “Business as usual” can be applied to this Circular Case.

Pre-cast concrete is produced at industrial scale pilot demonstration in SPRAL (concrete products manufacturing Portuguese SME), employing, as a filler, the lime ash generated by the NAVIGATOR COMPANY NAV (Pulp and Paper Company), located in Portugal. The new pre-cast concrete performance was compared with the specifications and standard pre-cast concretes. UNIVERSITY OF AVEIRO (UAVR) collaborated with SPRAL and NAV in this Circular Case, for technical support. Figure 1 shows the CC1 Circular Case in Portugal integrating the CC1a and CC1b (see factsheet CC1b). Figures 2 to 4 show the industrial scale pilot demonstration, and Tables 1 and 2 show CC main items, key factors and lessons learnt.

CC1a: Concrete pre-cast based on lime ash short Guidelines:

🚧 Circular Economy Models using lime ash derived from the energetic valorisation of PPI lime mud waste use in pre-cast concretes as developed in PAPERCHAIN approach (CC1a), are basically limited by its classification as “waste”, and lack of specific legal framework for lime ash use in pre-cast concretes production. Technical and environmental performance and workability according to usual pre-cast elaboration procedures have been proven to be successful, not increasing the process costs. Replicability potential of this CEM is considered of high across EU Ms.

FIGURE 1 – CC1 (PORTUGAL). CONSTRUCTION OF PRE-CAST CONCRETES AND ASPHALTS.

FIGURE 2 – WASTE. LIME-ASH DERIVED FROM THE INCINERATION OF PAPER LIME-MUD.

FIGURE 3 – PROCESS: CONCRETE REINFORCED PRE-CASTING BASED ON PAPER LIME-ASH.

FIGURE 4 – APPLICATION. CONCRETE PRE-CAST RE-ENFORCED BEAMS IN AND COLUMNS IN PORTICOS.

TABLE 1 PAPERCHAIN CIRCULAR CASE 1A MAIN ITEMS

<i>item</i>	<i>Description</i>
PAPERCHAIN STAKEHOLDERS	NAVIGATOR (waste producer), SPRAL (constructor), UAV (scientific partner)
LOCATION	Ilhavo (Portugal)
WASTE	Lime ash (waste paper result of energetic valorization of PPI lime mud)
PRODUCT	Pre-cast Concrete
APPLICATION	Columns and Beams for construction of porticos.

TABLE 2 CC1A LIME ASH CONCRETE PRE-CASTS. KEY FACTORS AND LESSONS LEARNT.

<i>Key Factor</i>	<i>Description</i>	<i>Lesson learnt</i>
Waste (Lime Ash)	<p>Composed mainly by calcium carbonate (CaCO₃);</p> <p>Code 03 03 09 in the European List of wastes (2014), classified as non-hazardous waste (decision 2014/955).</p>	<p>Needs no pre-treatment after lime-mud incineration.</p> <p>Relatively free of contaminants</p> <p>Very suitable material as filler</p>
Regulatory framework	<p>UNE-12620, Aggregates for concrete.</p> <p>EN 13225:2013 Precast concrete products (91.100.30 Concrete and concrete products) standard.</p>	<p>No specific regulation for the use of lime ash in pre-cast elements.</p> <p>License obtaining for waste valorization, even at pilot level constitutes nowadays a main barrier for circular cases implementation at Portugal.</p>
Proceedings	<p>“Bussiness as usual” for fillers employed on pre-cast concretes elaboration.</p>	<p>Easily introduced in concrete mixture.</p> <p>Good workability. Similar to natural filler production rate and performance of columns and beams. 100% of natural/standard filler replacement achievable.</p>

Barriers	Lack of specific regulation for lime-ash in pre-cast concretes is a major handicap for lime ash valorization.	Lime ash still considered as “waste”. CE marking (CEN route) foreseen as best route for this application.
Enablers	Present Process equipment and facilities employed in pre-cast elaboration with standard fillers are suitable with novel filler.	No substantial process modification. Relatively free of pollutants.
LCA/CO2 footprint	The features and characteristics of the targeted construction products were not hindered or modified by the introduction of these wastes after long term monitoring.	Proven technical and environmental performance and expected long-term performance, similar to those materials with natural fillers. No environmental threat. Lower CO ₂ footprint and increased circularity vs. standard .
Exploitation	<p>The pre-cast elaboration requires from a dry filler (<1%) providing, guaranteed by the incineration process of the lime mud to obtain lime ash stored in dry environment.</p> <p>Market introduction of the lime ash should be highly possible.</p>	<p>Not need to modify the pre-cast elaboration method, and then, no extra investment costs are needed.</p> <p>Competitive CEM if regular (dry) waste supply is provided.</p> <p>Regulatory support and incentives (taxes, green purchases, etc.) can be very variable among Ms. Regulatory in some countries can be a definite barrier for lime ash exploitation.</p>
Replicability potential	Concrete (limestone) fillers that are currently on the market, typically have a competitive cost and well-established extraction industries.	Key factors affecting the market potential such as technical feasibility of use and competitive cost could be successfully addressed by the PAPERCHAIN approach in most of the EU Ms.